

Discourse Structure of Shinzo Abe's Resignation Speech: Critical Discourse Analysis

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Abstract

This preliminary research aims to describe the discourse structure that overshadows the text of Shinzo Abe's resignation speech on August 28, 2020 taken from the official website of the Government Office of the Prime Minister of Japan. The research approaches are descriptive qualitative methodological approach and theoretical approach from Teun van Dijk's critical discourse analysis. It divides into three dimensions: the text dimension, the social cognition dimension, and the social context dimension. However, this research only focus on the text dimension of Shinzo Abe's resignation speech. Then, the data analysis process includes text structure analysis is consisting of three levels: macrostructure, superstructure, and microstructure. The results show that schematically, the text structure has been organized sequentially from opening, content, and closing. However, what can be underlined from the superstructure of Shinzo Abe's resignation speech is that the opening and closing paragraphs contain Shinzo Abe's gratitude to the Japanese people. Thematically, the text structure consists of two themes: coronavirus countermeasures and concerns over Shinzo Abe's health. From these two themes, through the strategies of setting, detail, intention, and presumption, the text of Shinzo Abe's resignation speech contains explicit meaning that Shinzo Abe describes the steps taken by the Japanese government to prevent the spread of the coronavirus. Shinzo Abe also describes the health condition of his illness chronologically because it is feared that he will not be able to complete his duties and obligations as prime minister, thus destabilizing all

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aspects of Japanese life due to his health. Therefore, Shinzo Abe resigned as prime minister before his term ended.

1. Introduction

On August 28, 2020, Shinzo Abe officially announced his resignation as prime minister of Japan, citing health concerns (BBC News, 2020). It was Shinzo Abe's second resignation as Prime Minister of Japan (Japan Times, 2020). The first resignation was announced when Shinzo Abe became Prime Minister of Japan for the first time in the 2006-2007 period for the same reason due to chronic ulcerative colitis or inflammation of the colon in his digestive system that he has experienced for a long time (Kyodo News, 2020). Shinzo Abe made the resignation announcement through a state speech at a press conference at the Prime Minister's Office. Shinzo Abe's resignation speech, which was considered sudden, became the world's attention because it triggered confusion about Japan's future government (Bloomberg, 2020). The confusion is also understandable because Shinzo Abe announced his resignation during the COVID-19 pandemic.

This research uses Shinzo Abe's resignation speech because he was in the spotlight and had drawn criticism due to handling the pandemic during his reign, which was considered less than optimal (Tempo, 2020). His support for falling to one of the lowest levels in his nearly eight years in office can be seen in his support. Japan did not experience a too sharp spike in COVID-19 cases compared to other countries, where the total number of Covid-19 cases recorded until August 2020 was around 67,000 cases with 1,255 deaths. However, Shinzo Abe's initial response to the coronavirus pandemic could have been more organized, which critics saw as a lack of leadership as COVID-19 infections spread (Kompas, 2020). It impacted the Tokyo Olympics, which was supposed to be held in 2020 but was eventually postponed to 2021 (Tempo, 2020).

As the longest-serving politician as prime minister in the history of the Japanese government, Shinzo Abe has a long political career because he was born into a political family. The length of his political career has honed Shinzo Abe's ability to make speeches. Keraf (1991) defines speech as direct persuasive communication between an orator and an audience. The definition is associated with West & Turner's (2008) statement that the communicative ability of the orator depends not only on whether the content of the material is interesting or not but also on how the material is delivered to influence the audience. Therefore, Keraf (1991) adds that this is an essential skill for orators in the political world because word choice supports the orator in formulating his ideas in addition to mastering the material.

Furthermore, Bulan & Kasman (2018) state that word choice in speech means producing language that the audience can interpret. In line with the definition given by Keraf (1991), Ayuningtias & Hartanto (2014) added that the language produced by orators has a communicative function and a persuasive function because whether or not the language is neutral depends on who the speaker is.

Language has an essential meaning in politics. Language is a powerful medium to instill ideology, seize/obtain, and maintain power (Asror, 2015). It aligns with Haryatmoko's (2016) statement that language is a medium for exercising ideological control and power. Various linguistic tools are used to gain sympathy, attract attention, and create perceptions of a problem, controlling the audience's thoughts, behavior, and values. Therefore, language functions as a means of exercising ideological and power control. The ideological inculcation and power control processes require language as a means of expression, such as political speeches, lectures, sermons, and advertisements.

However, language is not independently powerful; it gains power through the use of powerful orators and politicians, among others. Power is signaled, for example, by grammatical forms within

the text or genre of the text (Renkema, 2009). Similarly, Jupriono (2010) also asserts that speech as a text is an organized sign system in which language reflects certain attitudes, beliefs, and values. It explains why the language use of influential people can be studied critically and with careful observation.

The observation of language use in speech as a text can be studied in discourse analysis. The central concept of discourse analysis is focused on language use in the form of oral or written texts with the object of study in the form of language units that are larger than sentences and have context and cohesiveness, such as political speeches, recorded live conversations that have been scripted, debates, religious preaching meeting notes, lectures, and others.

Furthermore, Crystal (1987) and Fairclough (1995; 2013) state that discourse analysis is associated with text or spoken and written language. Crystal (1987) explains that discourse analysis is focused on natural structures based on the concept of spoken language in various forms of conversation, such as interviews and others. In contrast, the concept based on written language or text stated by Fairclough (1995; 2013) that discourse analysis is an effort to reveal the implied meaning of the subject (speaker, writer, or speaker) who gives a statement. The disclosure is carried out through researchers positioning themselves as subjects by tracing the meaning contained in the discourse so that the form of distribution and production of ideology disguised in it can be known. In this case, the distribution and production of ideology can be seen from the form of power relations towards the formation and representation displayed by the subject.

Some previous studies related to this research have been conducted, such as Bowo et al. (2022) discussed the image formed by Boris Johnson in his resignation speech as British Prime Minister; Kartika and Azis (2021) revealed politeness strategies in expressive speech acts in Shinzo Abe's resignation speech; Megah S. (2019) analyzed President Soeharto's speech when he resigned from the position of President of the Republic of Indonesia on May 21, 1998; and Setiawan (2016) described the form and features of suprasegmental morphemes in the text of Prabowo-Hatta's resignation speech from the 2014 presidential election. All previous studies discussed the resignation of state officials with different theoretical studies, such as the image of Boris Johnson's resignation with Norman Fairclough's critical discourse analysis (Bowo et al., 2022); Shinzo Abe's resignation speech politeness strategy with Searle's speech act theory (Kartika & Azis, 2021); language appraisal in Soeharto's resignation with appraisal analysis (Megah S., 2019); and the form and features of suprasegmental morphemes in the text of Prabowo-Hatta's resignation speech with speech act phonology analysis (Setiawan, 2016). Among the four previous studies, this research is similar to the research of Bowo et al. (2022) in the field of study and Kartika and Azis (2021) regarding the selection of state officials. However, in contrast to these two studies, this research will focus on Teun A. van Dijk's critical discourse analysis of Shinzo Abe's resignation speech which has yet to be explored in depth by Kartika and Azis (2021). Therefore, this study will describe the discourse structure that overshadows Shinzo Abe's resignation speech.

2. Materials and Methods

The data source of this research comes from Shinzo Abe's resignation speech on August 28, 2020. The data subject of this research is a fragment of Shinzo Abe's resignation speech text taken from the official website of the Government Office of the Prime Minister of Japan. The data collection method is divided into two, namely, the documentation method and the observation method. This research uses two approaches, namely a descriptive qualitative methodological approach and a theoretical approach from the critical discourse analysis model of Teun van Dijk, which divides critical discourse analysis into three dimensions.

1. The text dimension includes macro structure related to the meaning of the text, superstructure related to the scheme, and microstructure related to linguistic aspects,

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2. The social cognition dimension includes mental structure, meaning process, and mental, and
 3. The social context dimension includes power and access.

However, this research will focus on the text dimension of Shinzo Abe's resignation speech.

Based on Van Dijk's critical discourse analysis model, the data analysis process includes text and text structure analysis. In this case, van Dijk divides these discourse elements into three levels: macrostructure, superstructure, and microstructure. However, although it consists of various elements, all of them are a unity that is interrelated, related, and supportive of each other. From this analysis, it can be understood how to determine the structure of the text. The macrostructure is a text's global or general meaning that can be observed by looking at the topic or theme in a text. This theme underlies how the text is built, what meaning is to be emphasized, what sentences are used, what lexicon is chosen, and how it is conveyed.

All of these can be seen as superstructure and microstructure. Superstructure is a discourse structure that relates to the framework of a text, how parts are built and arranged as a whole consisting of opening, content, and closing. Microstructure is the meaning of discourse observed from small text parts in the form of lingual elements studied through semantics, syntax, stylistics, and rhetoric (van Dijk, 2014). However, this research will focus on the meaning studied through semantics as part of the microstructure.

3. Results and Discussions

The analysis results conducted on the text of Shinzo Abe's resignation speech based on two discourse structures proposed by van Dijk, namely macrostructure and superstructure, can be described as follows.

Macrostructure

At a macro level, Shinzo Abe's resignation speech is divided into two major topics or themes: coronavirus countermeasures and concerns over Shinzo Abe's health. It can be seen in Data 1.

Data 1

以上、2つのことを国民の皆様にご報告させていただいた上で、私自身の健康上の問題についてお話をさせていただきたいと思います。

Ijō, futatsu no koto o kokumin no minasama ni o hōkoku sa sete itadaita ue de, watakushijishin no kenkōjō no mondai ni tsuite ohanashi o sa sete itadakitai to omoimasu.

Having now reported to the people about those two issues, I would like to talk about the concern over my personal health.

Data 1 shows two major topics, *futatsu no koto* and *watashi jishin no kenkoujou no mondai*. The phrase of *futatsu no koto* refers to two subtopics, namely coronavirus countermeasures and the security environment around Japan. These two subtopics can be seen in the Data 2.

Data 2

コロナ対策と並んで一時の空白も許されないのが、我が国を取り巻く厳しい安全保障環境への対応であります。北朝鮮は弾道ミサイル能力を大きく向上させています。

Korona taisaku to narande ichiji no kūhaku mo yurusarenai no ga, wagakuni o torimaku kibishī anzen hoshō kankyō e no taiō de arimasu. Kitachōsen wa dandō misairu nōryoku o ōkiku kōjō sa sete imasu.

Along with our efforts to counter the coronavirus, our response to the severe security environment surrounding Japan does not permit any temporary vacuum. North Korea is making major improvements to its ballistic missile capabilities.

Data 2 shows that in addition to conveying the countermeasures taken by the government, Shinzo Abe also emphasized the security environment around Japan. The security conditions referred to by Shinzo Abe are related to North Korea's increasing ballistic missile capabilities.

Furthermore, the phrase *of watashi jishin no kenkoujou no mondai* in Data 1 is the second topic that refers to Shinzo Abe's health condition, as shown in Data 3.

Data 3

13年前、私の持病である潰瘍性大腸炎が悪化をし、僅か1年で突然、総理の職を辞することとなり、国民の皆様には大変な御迷惑をおかけいたしました。その後幸い新しい薬が効いて、体調は万全となり、そして国民の皆様から御支持を頂き、再び総理大臣の重責を担うこととなりました。この8年近くの間、しっかりと持病をコントロールしながら、何ら支障なく総理大臣の仕事に毎日、日々、全力投球することができました。

13-Nen mae, watashi no jibyō de aru kaiyōseidaichōen ga akka o shi, wazuka 1-nen de totsuzen, sōri no shoku o jisuru koto to nari, kokumin no minasama ni wa taihen'na gomeiwaku o okakeitashimashita. Sonogo saiwai atarashī kusuri ga kiite, taichō wa banzen to nari, soshite kokumin no minasama kara o shiji o itadaki, futatabi sōri daijin no jūseki o ninau koto to narimashita. Kono 8-nen chikaku no ma, shikkari to jibyō o kontorōru shinagara, nanra shishō naku sōri daijin no shigoto ni mainichi, hibi, Zenryoku tōkyū suru koto ga dekimashita.

Thirteen years ago, my chronic ulcerative colitis took a turn for the worse. In just one year, I suddenly resigned from the post of prime minister, causing great inconvenience among the public. Later, fortunately, a new drug was very effective, and I returned to great shape physically. I again took up the weighty responsibility of serving as prime minister thanks to support from the people. Over the last almost eight years I have kept my chronic illness fully under control and have had no trouble devoting all of my energy every day, day after day, to the job of prime minister.

Data 3 shows that Shinzo Abe tells his health condition chronologically. As a result of his illness, Shinzo Abe resigned as Prime Minister of Japan when he first took office in 2007. However, at that time, Shinzo Abe could only serve for one year. Thanks to medical advancements that resulted in new treatments, Shinzo Abe returned to office as prime minister of Japan in 2012 and remained in office for eight years.

It can be concluded that Shinzo Abe's resignation speech consists of two major topics: coronavirus countermeasures and concerns over Shinzo Abe's health. However, the topic or theme of coronavirus countermeasures is further divided into two subtopics, namely the coronavirus countermeasures themselves and the condition of the security environment around Japan. In contrast, the concerns over Shinzo Abe's health have no subtopics, as the content is focused on Shinzo Abe's health condition while undergoing treatment.

Superstructure

The superstructure relates to the text-building scheme. It looks at how the parts and sequences of the text are schematized or constructed as a whole. Generally, a text or discourse is built on three schemes: opening, body, and closing. Schematically, Shinzo Abe's resignation speech has a sequential scheme. The opening section is marked by an introductory paragraph, as shown in Data 4.

Data 4

猛暑が続く中、国民の皆様にはコロナウイルス対策、そして熱中症対策、ダブルの対策に万全を期していただいておりますこと、国や地方自治体から様々な要請に対して、自治体の様々な要請に対して御協力を頂いておりますことに心から感謝申し上げます。

Mōsho ga tsudzuku-chū, kokumin no minasama ni wa koronairusu taisaku, soshite netchūshō taisaku, daburu no taisaku ni banzen o kishite itadaite orimasu koto, kuni ya chihōjichitai kara samazamana yōsei ni taishite, jichitai no samazamana yōsei ni taishite o kyōryoku o itadaite orimasu koto ni kokorokara kansha mōshiagemasu.

I wish to thank the Japanese people sincerely for taking thorough measures to counter both the coronavirus and heatstroke as the intense heat continues, and for cooperating with various requests from the national and local governments.

Data 4 shows that Shinzo Abe started his speech by expressing his gratitude to the Japanese people for cooperating in responding to all policies provided by the Japanese government to prevent the transmission of the coronavirus.

The content part of Shinzo Abe's resignation speech is divided into two major themes or topics related to coronavirus countermeasures and concerns over Shinzo Abe's health. It can be seen in Data 1 and Data 2. A closing sentence in Data 5 characterizes the closing part.

Data 5

国民の皆様、8年近くにわたりまして、本当にありがとうございました。

Kokumin no minasama, 8-nen chikaku ni watarimashite, hontōni arigatō gozaimashita.

I thank the Japanese people sincerely for these eight years.

Data 5 shows that Shinzo Abe closed his speech with gratitude to the Japanese people for accepting him during his tenure as prime minister of Japan.

It can be concluded that Shinzo Abe's resignation speech has a sequential opening, body, and closing scheme. However, what can be underlined from the superstructure of Shinzo Abe's resignation speech is that the opening and closing paragraphs contain Shinzo Abe's gratitude to the Japanese people. Shinzo Abe begins his speech with gratitude to the people who have cooperated in responding to all policies provided by the Japanese government to prevent the transmission of the coronavirus in the opening paragraph. In contrast, Shinzo Abe closed his speech with gratitude to the Japanese people for accepting him during his tenure as prime minister of Japan.

Microstructure

Microstructure deals with the lingual elements that make up a text. These lingual elements are observed through semantics, syntax, stylistics, and rhetoric. However, this research will focus on the meaning studied through semantics.

Semantics

Semantic observation examines the speech text's setting, details, purpose, and presupposition. This observation will decipher the meaning that the orator wants to emphasize with the writing strategies of setting, detail, intention, and presupposition from the text of Shinzo Abe's resignation speech.

Setting

The setting is not only related to what events are behind the realization of a text. The setting is also a part of the discourse that can influence the meaning the speaker wants to display and convey to the public. In addition, the setting can reveal the purpose of the speaker because the setting used or chosen determines where the audience's view is to be directed by the orator. Therefore, orators sometimes do not display the intent of the text explicitly. Here is some data on the setting in Shinzo Abe's resignation speech.

Data 6

コロナウイルス対策につきましては、今年の1月から正体不明の敵と悪戦苦闘する中、少しでも感染を抑え、極力重症化を防ぎ、そして国民の命を守るため、その時々々の知見の中で最善の努力を重ねてきたつもりであります。

Koronairusu taisaku ni tsukimashiteha, kotoshi no ichi gatsu kara shōtai fumei no teki to akusenkutō suru Chū, sukoshidemo kansen o osae, kyokuryoku jūshō-ka o fusegi, soshite kokumin no inochi o mamoru tame, sono tokidoki no chiken no naka de saizen no doryoku o kasanete kita tsumori de arimasu.

With regard to coronavirus countermeasures, while we have been in a tough fight against a faceless enemy since this January, we have made our best efforts given the knowledge we had at the time to reduce the number of infections as much as possible, prevent patients from developing severe symptoms to the greatest possible extent, and protect people's lives.

In addition to the background of Shinzo Abe's claim to prevent the spread of the coronavirus, this speech also has the background of Shinzo Abe's health condition. Data 3 shows that Shinzo Abe wants to convey his deteriorating health condition by mentioning the name of his disease, namely *kaiyōseidaichōen* or chronic ulcerative colitis disease that he has had since he was a teenager. After 13 years, Shinzo Abe's health condition was declared to have improved with the latest treatment. It turned out that the disease had relapsed, and Shinzo Abe had to undergo regular medical check-ups. Shinzo Abe recounts the chronology of his medical check-up as shown in Detail of Data 8.

Detail

Detail relates to the control of the information displayed by the orator. It is the orator's strategy of expressing his attitude explicitly and implicitly about the processed information. The orator will convey which parts are described in full and which are described in less. Full and lengthy details will

be used as highlights. It will be considered good information for the orator and will be presented in full along with supporting facts, thus revealing the orator's intentions. Therefore, favorable information is presented explicitly, while unfavorable information is presented implicitly. Here are some data related to details in Shinzo Abe's resignation speech.

Data 7

本日、夏から秋、そして冬の到来を見据えた今後のコロナ対策を決定いたしました。この半年で多くのことが分かってきました。3密を徹底的に回避するといった予防策により、社会経済活動との両立は十分に可能であります。

Honjitsu, natsu kara aki, soshite fuyu no tōrai o misueta kongo no korona taisaku o kettei itashimashita. Kono hantoshi de ōku no koto ga wakatte kimashita. San mitsu o tetteiteki ni kaihi suru to itta yobō-saku ni yori, shakai keizai katsudō to no ryōritsu wa jūbun ni kanōdearimasu.

Today we decided on future coronavirus countermeasures that anticipate the shift from summer into autumn and the arrival of winter. Over the last six months, we have come to understand many things. By taking preventive measures, such as diligently avoiding the three Cs, it is fully possible to successfully fight the coronavirus while engaging in socioeconomic activities.

The efforts to prevent the spread of the coronavirus referred to by Shinzo Abe in Data 6 can be seen in Data 7 in the sentence of *san mitsu o tetteiteki ni kaihi suru to itta yobō-saku ni yori, shakai keizai katsudō to no ryōritsu wa jūbun ni kanōdearimasu*. The sentence shows that Shinzo Abe has given instructions to the Japanese people to avoid the three densities entirely.

Data 8

しかし、本年6月の定期検診で再発の兆候が見られると指摘を受けました。その後も薬を使いながら全力で職務に当たってまいりましたが、先月中旬頃から体調に異変が生じ、体力をかなり消耗する状況となりました。そして、8月上旬には潰瘍性大腸炎の再発が確認されました。今後の治療として、現在の薬に加えまして更に新しい薬の投与を行うことといたしました。今週初めの再検診においては、投薬の効果があるということは確認されたものの、この投薬はある程度継続的な処方が必要であり、予断は許しません。

Shikashi, hon'nen rokka getsu no teiki kenshin de saiatsu no chōkō ga mi rareru to shiteki o ukemashita. Sonogo mo kusuri o tsukainagara zenryoku de shokumu ni atatte mairimashitaga, sengetsu naka goro kara taichō ni ihen ga shōji, tairyoku o kanari shōmō suru jōkyō to narimashita. Soshite, hachi gatsu jōjun ni wa kaiyōseidaichōen no saiatsu ga kakunin sa remashita. Kongo no chiryō to shite, genzai no kusuri ni kuwaemashite sarani atarashī kusuri no tōyo o okonau koto to itashimashita. Konshū hajime no sai kenshin ni oite wa, tōyaku no kōka ga aru to iu koto wa kakunin sa reta mono no, kono tōyaku wa aruteido keizoku-tekina shohō ga hitsuyōdeari, yodan wa yurushimasen.

However, I was told during a regular checkup in June that symptoms of a relapse could be seen. Since that time I have continued to devote all my energies to my duties while taking medicine, but from roughly the middle of July something unusual happened to me health-wise, and I began to get quite physically exhausted. Then, at the beginning of August a

relapse of my ulcerative colitis was confirmed. As for my treatment from now, a new drug has been added to the medication I have been taking until now. At the re-examination I underwent at the beginning of this week, this new drug was confirmed to be effective. But it is necessary to have this medicine administered continuously for a while and it is difficult to foresee the result.

The chronology of health check-ups referred to by Shinzo Abe in Data 3 can be seen in Data 8, where Shinzo Abe mentions the routine check-up schedule chronologically with pronominals of time starting in *hon'nen rokka getsu*-June this year, *sengetsu naka goro*-the middle of last month, *hachi gatsu jōjun*-early August, and *konshū hajime*-early this week.

Intention

The intent element is similar to the detail element. The detail element relies on the appearance of fact-boosting information. Meanwhile, the intent element looks at whether the text is presented explicitly or not and whether the facts are presented nakedly or not. Otherwise, adverse information will be described in a cryptic, implicit, and hidden manner. The goal is that the public is only presented with favorable information to the communicator.

When associated with the element of detail in Shinzo Abe's speech, it can be seen that the phrase *san mitsu* in the sentence *san mitsu o tetteiteki ni kaihi suru to itta yobō-saku ni yori, shakai keizai katsudō to no ryōritsu wa jūbun ni kanōdearimasu* in Data 7 is implicitly conveyed by Shinzo Abe because the phrase was already mentioned in the second press conference speech on March 14, 2020. It contradicts the statement that harmful information is conveyed implicitly because the phrase of *san mitsu* is not harmful information. Instead, it is beneficial information for Japanese people as a guide to avoiding overcrowding. In contrast to the detail element in Data 8, it can be seen that the information conveyed by Shinzo Abe is explicitly mentioned regarding the routine inspection schedule in the form of a pronominal of time.

Presupposition

Presuppositions are statements that can be used to support the meaning of the text. Presuppositions present statements that are seen as reliable and, therefore, unquestionable. Theoretically, presupposition B of sentence A is the presupposition entailed by A and non-A. It is a statement used to support the meaning of the text by providing a believable premise (Van Dijk, 1988: 63).

The presupposition is found in the speech delivered by Shinzo Abe, in the sentence *Kitachōsen wa dandō misairu nōryoku o ōkiku kōjō sa sete imasu* in Data 2. The presupposition in Data 2 is that Shinzo Abe's statement is considered reliable regarding North Korea's ballistic missiles, so there is no need to question it. The premise in the previous sentence reinforces the statement, *Korona taisaku to narande ichiji no kūhaku mo yurusarenai no ga, wagakuni o torimaku kibishī anzen hoshō kankyō e no taiō de arimasu*. Shinzo Abe delivered the premise because Shinzo Abe obtained information that North Korea, a neighboring country of Japan, apparently has plans to improve its ballistic missile capabilities. It will disrupt Japan's security stability during the COVID-19 pandemic.

It can be concluded that the strategies of setting, detail, intention, and presumption used by Shinzo Abe in his resignation speech contain explicit meaning that Shinzo Abe describes the steps of efforts taken by the Japanese government to prevent the spread of the coronavirus. Shinzo Abe also describes the health condition of his illness chronologically because it is feared that he will not be able to complete his duties and obligations as prime minister, thus destabilizing all aspects of Japanese life due to his health. Therefore, Shinzo Abe resigned as prime minister before his term ended.

4. Conclusion

The results of the analysis of the text of Shinzo Abe's resignation speech show that schematically, the text structure has been arranged sequentially from the opening, content, and closing. However, what can be underlined from the superstructure of Shinzo Abe's resignation speech is that the opening and closing paragraphs contain Shinzo Abe's gratitude to the Japanese people. Thematically, the text structure consists of two themes: coronavirus countermeasures and concerns over Shinzo Abe's health. From these two themes, through the strategies of setting, detail, intention, and presumption, the text of Shinzo Abe's resignation speech contains explicit meaning that Shinzo Abe describes the steps taken by the Japanese government to prevent the spread of the coronavirus. Shinzo Abe also describes the health condition of his illness chronologically because it is feared that he will not be able to complete his duties and obligations as prime minister, thus destabilizing all aspects of Japanese life due to his health. Therefore, Shinzo Abe resigned as prime minister before his term ended.

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